

A versatile approach for the synthesis of 1-methyl-4*H*[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-*a*][1,4]benzodiazepine *N*⁵-oxide

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Two routes for the synthesis of 1-methyl-4*H*[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-*a*][1,4]benzodiazepine *N*⁵-oxide (8) from 1,3-dihydro-2*H*-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one (2) have been described.

Since the discovery of the potent central nervous system activity in [1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-*a*][1,4]benzodiazepines, this system has undergone an extensive chemical investigation and several synthetic routes to this tricyclic skeleton have been developed¹⁻³. Of the many successful structural changes tried and tested since benzodiazepine CNS activity was discovered in late 1950's, almost all of them have 7-chloro and 5-aryl substituents. In addition to this, compounds were synthesized which contained a 2-oxo group. The presence of 7-substituent alongwith 5-aryl and 2-oxo groups were believed to be of paramount importance for psychopharmacological activity⁴. The same trend is apparent in the enormous amount of work which has been done on the synthesis of annelated 1,4-benzodiazepines, where the synthetic methods have been devised which ensured the presence of these functionalities in the final product. This concept was found to be untenable with the discovery of pyrrolo-1,4-benzodiazepine class of anti-tumour antibiotics⁵ such as anthramycin, sibiromycin, tomaymycin, neothramycin and chicamycin which although lacked the 5-aryl and 7-chloro substituents in their molecule showed physiological activity which was in no way less than any of the known tricyclic 1,4-benzodiazepines bearing the traditional substituents.

A survey of the methods on the synthesis of *s*-triazolo-1,4-benzodiazepines reveals that no attempt has been made in the literature to develop convenient routes for the preparation of compounds which lacked the 5-aryl and 7-chloro substituents though such compounds were important from the structure-activity relationship point of view. This prompted us to synthesize these molecules through the routes shown in Schemes 1 and 2.

With the requisite bicyclic benzodiazepine 2 in hand, the annelation of the triazole ring was quite straight for-

ward (Scheme 1). It has been reported recently⁶ that 1,3-dihydro-2*H*-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one (2) is formed conveniently in one step from *N*-chloroacetyl isatin (1). We employed 2 as a foundation and built the triazole ring on to it through the standard procedures^{1,7} known in the literature.

Results and discussion

1,3-Dihydro-2*H*-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one (2)⁶ was treated with P₂S₅ in pyridine to give the mercapto derivative, which was known to exist in its tautomeric thione form 3. The 2-mercapto was converted to the corresponding 2-ethylmercapto compound (4) by treatment with ethyl iodide. The title compound was prepared from 4 by two methods as shown in Scheme 1. Method A consisted of treating the 2-ethyl mercapto compound (4) with hydrazine hydrate to give the 2-hydrazinyl derivative (5). Treatment of 5 with ethyl orthoformate completed the formation of the triazole ring in 6. Method B involved the thermal cyclocondensation of 4 with acet-hydrazide to give the 1-methyltriazolobenzodiazepine derivative 7. Oxidation of 7 with MCPBA⁸ formed

Scheme 1

N^5 -oxide derivative **8**. In an alternative synthesis, the formation of N^5 -oxide function preceded to the elaboration of the tricyclic ring system as shown in Scheme 2. In this procedure **2** was converted to **9** by oxidation with MCPBA⁸. Treatment of **9** with P_2S_5 in pyridine gave the thione derivative **10** which was converted to the corresponding *S*-ethyl derivative **11**. Treatment of **11** with acet-hydrazide yielded tricyclic N^5 -oxide derivataive **8**. Melting point and spectral data of **8** obtained from both the procedures were same.

Scheme 2

The IR spectra of all the compounds showed characteristic C=N absorptions around 1580–1605 cm^{-1} . One of the noteworthy feature of the 1H NMR spectra of compounds **6-8** deserves to be specially mentioned. The enantiotropic C_3 methylene protons of these compounds showed an AB quartet (with coupling constant J_{AB} 14 Hz) which is in accord with the similar pattern observed for other [1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-*a*][1,4]benzodiazepines, apparently due to their magnetic nonequivalence character arising from C=N anisotropy in a preferred conformation of the molecule^{1,9}. The corresponding C_3 methylene protons of **2-5** and **9-11**, however, showed a doublet suggesting a diminished conformational rigidity in these molecules. The other IR and 1H NMR data of the compounds **2-11** were found to be in good agreement to the structures proposed for these molecules.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The purity of all the compounds was checked by TLC using the solvent systems (chloroform : methanol, 9 : 1, v/v) and silica gel-G as adsorbent. IR spectra were recorded on Pye Unicam Model SP3-300 infracord in nujol and on KBr pellets. 1H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian EM 360 L using $CDCl_3$ and $DMSO-d_6$ as the solvent and TMS as internal reference.

Synthesis of 1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-thione (3) :

A solution of **2**⁶ (1.60 g, 0.01 mol) and phosphorus pentasulfide (4.44 g, 0.01 mol) in pyridine (30.00 ml) was heated under reflux for 3 h at 90° in a nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and

extracted with chloroform. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated to give a yellow solid which was recrystallized from chloroform to give 1.09 g of **3** (62%), m.p. 247.5° (Found : C, 61.59; H, 4.20; N, 15.47. Calcd. for $C_9H_8N_2S$ (176.0) : C, 61.37; H, 4.54; N, 15.90%); ν_{max} 3170 (-NH), 1615 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 11.15 (1H, br, -NH), 7.95–7.00 (4H, m, ArH), 8.50 (1H, m, H-C=N), 3.01 (1H, d, J 1.5 Hz, -CH₂-).

Synthesis of 3H-2-ethyl mercapto-1,4-benzodiazepine (4) :

To a solution of **3** (3.52 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (30.00 ml) was added 1*N* sodium hydroxide (3.5 ml) and ethyl iodide (4.65 g, 0.03 mol). The mixture was heated on water bath for 2.5 h and evaporated to one-fourth of its volume, water (10 ml) was added and the product was extracted with methylene chloride. The solid obtained after evaporation of the solvent was recrystallized from ethanol-hexane mixture to give 2.89 g of **4** (71%), m.p. 185° (Found : C, 64.62; H, 5.12; N, 13.87. Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{12}N_2S$ (204.0) : C, 64.70; H, 5.88; N, 13.74%); ν_{max} 1620–1605 (C=N), 1460 and 1345 cm^{-1} (-CH₂CH₃); δ 7.80–6.92 (4H, m, ArH), 8.25 (1H, m, H-C=N), 2.79 (3H, t, *S*-ethyl), 1.41 (2H, q, *S*-ethyl), 2.85 (2H, d, J 1.5 Hz, -CH₂-).

Synthesis of 3H-2-hydrazino-1,4-benzodiazepine (5) :

A mixture of **4** (4.08 g, 0.02 mol), hydrazine hydrate (10.0 ml) and ethanol (50 ml) was heated at reflux temperature for 48 h. Removal of the solvent afforded a solid which was recrystallized from methanol to give 1.63 g of **5** (47%), m.p. 168° (Found : C, 61.99; H, 5.63; N, 32.36. Calcd. for $C_9H_{10}N_4$ (174.0) : C, 62.06; H, 5.75; N, 32.18%); ν_{max} 3330–3305 (-NHNH₂), 1625–1610 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 7.60–6.90 (4H, m, ArH), 7.98 (1H, m, H-C=N), 4.92 (3H, m, -NHNH₂), 4.15 (2H, d, J 1.5 Hz, -CH₂-).

Synthesis of 4H[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-*a*][1,4]benzodiazepine (6) :

A mixture of **5** (1.74 g, 0.01 mol) and ethyl orthoformate (16.0 ml, 0.01 mol) was heated at 130° for 3.5 h. Excess of ethyl orthoformate was removed under reduced pressure and the residual oil was triturated with anhydrous ether. The solid obtained was recrystallized from benzene to give 1.39 g of **6** (76%), m.p. 153° (Found : C, 65.38; H, 4.12; N, 30.50. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_8N_4$ (184.0) : C, 65.21; H, 4.35; N, 30.43%); ν_{max} 3020 (aromatic CH), 1605–1535 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 7.30–6.82 (4H, m, ArH), 8.43 (1H, m, H-C=N), 8.91 (1H, s, CH of triazole ring), 4.92 and 5.59 (2H, dd, J 14 Hz, -CH₂-).

Synthesis of 1-methyl-4H[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-*a*][1,4]benzodiazepine (7) :

To a solution of **4** (2.04 g, 0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was added acet-hydrazide (0.74 g, 0.01 mol) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 92 h. Removal of solvent from the reaction mixture afforded a syrup which was dissolved in chloroform (10 ml) and diluted with petroleum ether to give crude product. It was recrystallized from chloroform to give 1.16 g of **7** (59%), m.p. 238° (Found : C, 66.87; H, 4.86; N, 28.27. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₀N₄ (198.0) : C, 66.66; H, 5.06; N, 28.28%); ν_{\max} 1610–1570 (C=N), 1485 cm⁻¹ (CH₃); δ 7.25–6.80 (4H, m, ArH), 8.40 (1H, m, H-C=N), 2.63 (3H, s, CH₃ at C₁), 4.13 and 5.27 (2H, dd, *J* 14 Hz, -CH₂-).

Synthesis of 1-methyl-4H[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a][1,4]benzodiazepine N⁵-oxide (8) :

A solution of **7** (5.94 g, 0.03 mol) in methylene chloride (175 ml) was stirred at room temperature with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (1.72 g, 0.01 mol) for 2.5 h. Mixture was extracted with 3 × 100 ml of 1 *N* HCl. The extracts were washed with ether, made alkaline with ammonia and extracted with methylene chloride. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the product was recrystallized from ethyl acetate to give 2.63 g of **8** (41%), m.p. 302° (d) (Found : C, 61.53; H, 4.87; N, 26.09. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₀N₄O (214.0) : C, 61.69; H, 4.67; N, 26.16%); ν_{\max} 1615–1560 (C=N), 1470 (CH₃), 1259 cm⁻¹ (N-O); δ 7.39–6.82 (4H, m, ArH), 8.45 (1H, m, H-C=N), 3.05 (3H, s, CH₃ at C₁), 4.65 and 5.51 (2H, dd, *J* 14 Hz, -CH₂-).

Synthesis of 1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-one N⁴-oxide (9) :

A solution of **2** (1.60 g, 0.01 mol) in methylene chloride (60 ml) was stirred with *m*-chloroperbenzoic acid (3.44 g, 0.02 mol) for 1.5 h. Mixture was extracted with 3 × 25 ml 1 *N* HCl. The extracts were washed with ether, made alkaline with ammonia and extracted with methylene chloride. The solid which was obtained on drying and evaporation of solvent was recrystallized from chloroform to give 0.58 g of **9** (33%), m.p. 284° (Found : C, 61.20; H, 4.15; N, 16.02. Calcd. for C₉H₈N₂O₂ (176.0) : C, 61.36; H, 4.55; N, 15.90%); ν_{\max} 3410 (-NH), 1710 (CO of amide), 1260 cm⁻¹ (N-O); δ 11.55 (1H, br, -NH), 8.00–7.01 (4H, m, ArH), 8.40 (1H, m, H-C=N), 4.1 (2H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, -CH₂-).

Synthesis of 1,3-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzodiazepin-2-thione N⁴-oxide (10) :

Phosphorus pentasulphide (4.44 g, 0.01 mol) was added to a stirred solution of **9** (1.76 g, 0.01 mol) in pyridine (30 ml) in nitrogen atmosphere. The reaction mixture was heated to 90° and held at this temperature for 2.5 h. The mixture

was cooled and poured into ice cold water (500 ml). The solid obtained was filtered, washed successively with 30 ml of 3 *N* HCl and 50 ml of water and air dried. It was recrystallized from chloroform to give 0.90 g of **10** (47%), m.p. 244° (Found : C, 56.57; H, 4.53; N, 14.57. Calcd. for C₉H₈N₂OS (192.0) : C, 56.25; H, 4.17; N, 14.58%); ν_{\max} 3390 (-NH), 1700 (CO of amide), 1255 cm⁻¹ (N-O); δ 11.59 (1H, br, -NH), 8.80–7.15 (4H, m, ArH), 8.60 (1H, m, H-C=N), 4.3 (2H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, -CH₂-).

Synthesis of 3H-2-ethyl mercapto-1,4-benzodiazepine N⁴-oxide (11) :

To a solution of **10** (3.84 g, 0.02 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was added 1 *N* NaOH (4.7 ml) and ethyl iodine (4.65 g, 0.03 mol). The mixture was heated on the water bath for 3 h and evaporated to one-fourth of its volume, water (20 ml) was added. The product was extracted with methylene chloride. Solvent was evaporated and the solid obtained was recrystallized from benzene to give 2.42 g of **11** (55%), m.p. 208° (Found : C, 60.00; H, 5.14; N, 12.70. Calcd. for C₁₁H₁₂N₂OS (220.0) : C, 60.00; H, 5.45; N, 12.73%); ν_{\max} 1690 (C=N), 1265 (N-O), 1460 and 1345 cm⁻¹ (-CH₂CH₃); δ 8.90–7.00 (4H, m, ArH), 8.45 (1H, m, H-C=N), 2.85 (3H, t, *S*-ethyl), 1.49 (2H, q, *S*-ethyl) 4.3 (2H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, -CH₂-).

Alternative procedure for the synthesis of 1-methyl-4H[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a][1,4]benzodiazepine N⁵-oxide (8) :

A solution of **11** (2.20 g, 0.01 mol) and acet-hydrazide (0.74 g, 0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was heated at reflux temperature for 98 h. The reaction mixture was evaporated to give a syrup which was dissolved in acetone and diluted with petroleum ether to give a solid. It was recrystallized from ethyl acetate to give 0.83 g of **8** (39%), m.p. 302° (d).

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